

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: in this article, the factors that influence critical thinking and its development and their importance in the educational process are scientifically based. Alternatively, knowledge such as how critical thinking occupies a place in youth life and how it can find solutions to problems, how it reacts to the thoughts expressed has been consistently and scientifically substantiated.

Keywords: critical thinking, factor, time, educational process, mutual exchange of ideas, information, activity, colorfulness, permission, risk, value.

The policy of education and upbringing at the same time requires a new social order. Currently, our society demands individuals who quickly rebuild and find a way out of a difficult situation by creating ideas. Deep changes in modern education are putting the use of new technologies of education and upbringing as a priority. The formation of critical thinking skills in students is influenced not only by the social environment, but also by several other factors. Today, our educators and parents demand that we not only pay special attention to the education of young people, but also talk more with them, and at the same time encourage our young people to think critically. In this regard, our country is undergoing several reforms in the field of Education. A clear example of this is decree PD-5847 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 on approval of the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030, resolution PD-4199 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.02.2019 on measures for the establishment of presidential schools, We can see that the decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 06.11.2020 "on additional measures to further improve the educational system" PD-4884 serve to further develop and improve the educational system.

Critical thinking is the development of reliable and reasonable assessments of what is appropriate for us to believe and deny. Critical thinking employs the tools of logic and science, as it values doubt in a rational attitude from insecurity or dogmatism, undeniable trust, science intelligence, and dream thinking. Criticism is the assessment of something or someone's shortcomings, negative thinking about what or someone. Criticism of others is the desire to match their attitude to the problem being considered with yours. Have you ever thought about questions that can develop critical thinking? Questions like this encourage a new way of thinking, limiting ourselves to the range of guessing and thinking that we are used to. They lead us to discovery, research and great dreams. Criticism (kritika (lot-judging skill) – assessment, analysis of an event related to some area of human activity. It consists in finding and discussing mistakes. This usually leads to manmanism. Others do not want to accept the opinions of the critic for being brought up in this spirit. Hence, criticism is an encroachment

on the information and energy world of others. Critical thinking is primarily formed through discussion, written work, and active work with texts.

At the same time, the following factors are important in the development of critical thinking: Time. Critical thinking it certainly takes time. Pearson, Hansen, Gordon (1979) argue that the creation of one's own fiction leads as if to archaeologically Research an earlier idea, imagination, encounters, and experiences. Hence:

- express their thoughts in their own words;
- mutual exchange of critical opinions;
- being able to express their beauty and receive answers to constructive suggestions;
- to be able to realize thoughts in the guise of certain ideas, in a comfortable environment and to express their ideas fully and clearly.

Permission. In order for there to be freedom in critical thinking, students-young people should receive permission to say something acceptable and unacceptable, think about them, create. Student-young people actively engage in critical analysis once they are aware of the circumstances in which they are allowed. Permission to critical analysis is based on the principle of awareness. In this case, the difference between analysis and overstrain should be clarified. Critical thinking is given in a friendly and effective setting, where permission is a genuine goal for thinking.

Colour. In the process of thinking of students-young people, various thoughts and ideas arise. Colorful thoughts and ideas arise only when the idea of the existence of a single answer is eliminated. When the expression of thoughts is limited, the thinking of the reader-youth is put to an end. In the presence of only one answer, it is worth using a variety of tools and processes, with the help of which the reader-youth can find this answer.

Activism. Critical thinking is directly linked to student-youth activism. Usually, students-young people are slow listeners, because they are educated by the teacher or the text reflects this knowledge of him, thanks to which the belief that their knowledge is responsible for the teacher is formed. The active participation of the student-youth in the educational process and their willingness to be responsible for their studies give the expected results in critical thinking. A pedagogical approach, such as encouraging student-youth to reflect, to share their ideas and thoughts, cultivates their activism. Mikhail Chikzhentmikhaly (1975) notes that if students actively participate in the learning process at that complex level, they will receive a great appreciation for their participation in the process of cognition and feel a deep sense of satisfaction in themselves.

Risk. Freethought is based on risk. It is necessary to encourage people who take risks without fear in his cognitive activity.. In the process of thinking, there may also be cases when "stupid ideas" are not concocted by reason, and concepts are put forward. The teacher should explain this to the student-youth as a natural state of the educational process. It is necessary to make sure that it is necessary to think in an environment where students-young people are at risk-free, that is, ideas are valued, where active participation of student-young people in thinking activities is highly motivating.

Est. One of the factors of critical thinking is the appreciation of the thinking process of the student-youth. In the organized thinking process, student-young people respond to deep responsibility and attention, realizing that their ideas, their imagination are appreciated by the teacher. Student-young people try to demonstrate an appreciation for their thinking process, begin to take it seriously and its consequences.

Value. During the organization of the thought process, it is necessary to instill in their minds that the results of their thoughts, their own critical analysis, are valuable. The teacher should be free of ready-made molds, templates when requiring students-young people to simply process a particular material. This leads the reader-youth to make sure that mechanically reworking other ideas is the most important and valuable. In fact, it is necessary to be able to show the reader-youth that their own opinion, ideas and visions that apply to themselves are valuable. It is necessary for the student-young people themselves to be able to make sure that their thoughts are valuable. They must recognize that their opinion is considered extremely important in the process of discussing the concept and issue, as well as a significant contribution.

Mutual exchange of ideas. The thought process contemplates the exchange of ideas between students and young people. The mutual exchange of ideas of the student-youth forms the basis for their mutual sharing in learning from each other. As a thinker, student-young people are required to reveal to others their abilities for major thought and simple error that they have. Exchange of views also requires the reader-youth to listen carefully, forcibly transfer his or her system of views to the speaker, and refrain from correcting other speakers. In response, the student-youth will be able to take advantage of the gross opinions of others. As a result of a wide range of discussion, the reader-young people have a greater ability to analyze and identify ideas that belong to them, and drag them into the system of ideas that they have created in their knowledge and life experiences. There are several models of its conduct in the organization of the thought process. They are:

- self-confidence;
- active participation in work;
- exchange of ideas with comrades and teacher;
- being able to listen to other people's opinion.

In the place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of methods of Information Communication, thinking and thinking gives the opportunity to solve the following important tasks:

- reader-helps young people to realize their goals;
- ensures activity in training;
- calls for effective discussion;
- the reader-helps so that the young people themselves can draw up questions and ask it in a question style;
- reader-helps young people express their personal knowledge;
- -supports the motivation of the personal reading of the reader-youth;
- creates a mood of respect for any thoughts;
- reader-helps to cultivate the anguish that characters have in young people;
- reader-creates conditions for thinking that are valued in young people;

It is most important to have the ability to target and motivate one's own critical thinking, to be able to actively manage one's own desires, to appreciate the time each minute is used to improve one's own personality. Taken in this respect, at the same time as today's globalization and development, the educational process will also develop if we form it in young educators who are developing, as the development of critical thinking is one of the requirements of the period.

It is better to avoid the problem than to try to avoid problems, because critical thinking also emphasizes careful thinking - it does not mean jumping to the conclusion to avoid you. Go ahead and recognize the presence of a clear conclusion, as it may be correct, but do not accept it until you consider other options.

In short, all this is a short summary of some of the main characteristics that people need to develop to think critically and suspiciously. While this may not seem immediate, it does not require a degree in philosophy or science to be a good critical thinker. Some education is required on basic issues, but there is no work of the average person.

Some aspects of basic logic can be difficult, but in the end there is only one way to get comfortable with it: practice. For example, you can forget to make wrong names come true. Instead, you need to carefully read the evidence and learn to identify mistakes. The more time you spend on it, the more natural it will be, and you will remember the names of mistakes.

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